

In Vitro Antisickling and Free Radical Scavenging Activities of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* Benth (Fabaceae)

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ABSTRACT

The use of medicinal plants for the treatment and prevention of human diseases including Sickle Cell Disease is an old indigenous technology in Africa. *Pentaclethra macrophylla* is traditionally used in Congolese folk medicine to treat Sickle Cell Disease. The aim of the present study was to evaluate the antisickling and radical scavenging activities of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem barks using Emmel's test and the radical DPPH assay.

The results showed that n-hexane, dichloromethane and methanol soluble fractions exhibited interesting antisickling activity compared to that of ethyl acetate soluble fraction, as revealed by the observed normal biconcave form of sickle erythrocyte in hypoxic conditions. On the other hand, the ethyl acetate and methanol soluble fractions revealed a significant radical scavenging activity. The methanol soluble fraction exhibited a promising antiradical activity ($IC_{50} = 1.517 \pm 0.053 \mu\text{g/mL}$). The chemical screening performed on this plant species revealed the presence of anthocyanins and organic acids which were then extracted. Total anthocyanins and organic acids revealed interesting antisickling and antioxidant properties, thus justifying the use of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* in Congolese traditional healers to treat Sickle Cell Disease. In the best of our knowledge, *Pentaclethra macrophylla* has not been yet scientifically validated as antisickling plant in Democratic Republic of the Congo.

Keyword: Sickle cell disease, Traditional medicine, *Pentaclethra macrophylla*, anthocyanins, organic acids.

INTRODUCTION

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is a genetic and hereditary disease in which a mutation in the gene encoding the human β -globin subunit results in replacement of $\beta 6$ glutamic acid by valine, leading to the formation of abnormal hemoglobin, Hb S. This amino acid substitution alters not only the affinity of hemoglobin toward oxygen but also its solubility under low oxygen pressure conditions. In these conditions, the sickle hemoglobin polymerizes and forms a rigid chain that distorts the biconcave disc shaped erythrocyte into a sickle shape, responsible of the devastating clinical manifestations of the disease [1-3]. Each year about 300,000 children are born with pathological hemoglobin of which 70% are affected by SCD. Most of them die before the age of five years when they do not receive regular

medical care. In Democratic Republic of the Congo, almost 2% of the population are sicklers [3-5].

Clinical management of SCD includes medullar transplantation, repeated blood transfusion, the use of hydroxyurea and anti-malarial prophylaxis. Unfortunately, all these current proposed therapies are limited and even not efficient. Some are quite expensive; others are toxic and have attendant risk factors [6, 7]. Thus, there is an urgent need to find alternative strategy with affordable and efficient novel drug agents. Alternative strategy in the management of SCD is now focusing on the identification of novel antisickling agents mainly that from medicinal plants. Indeed, traditional medicine continues to play a very significant role in the medical primary health care implementation in developing countries, especially in Africa [8].

In previous works, our research team showed that many medicinal plants used in traditional medicine in DRC to manage SCD had *in vitro* antisickling activity and that this activity is mainly due to anthocyanins [9-16]. As several other flavonoids, anthocyanins are powerful free radical scavengers and show antioxidant activity [19, 21]. Our previous studies have also identified organic acids as antisickling agents [11, 17].

Pentaclethra macrophylla known under the vernacular name of “Ngansi” (Kikongo) is traditionally used by the local communities to manage SCD. So, the present study was performed with the aim of evaluating the antisickling and antioxidant activities of *P. macrophylla* in order to validate scientifically its use in Congolese folk medicine. For the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on the antisickling and free radical scavenging activities of anthocyanins and organic acids extracts from *Pentaclethra macrophylla*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material collection and identification

The stem barks of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* Benth.(figure 1) were collected from plants growing around the Congo river, in Bas Fleuve region (Bas-Congo province, Democratic Republic of the Congo) in March 2012 and were authenticated by Botanist Mr B.L. Nlandu of the INERA (Institut National d’Etudes et Recherches Agronomiques). Voucher specimen is on deposit at the INERA Herbarium of the Faculty of Science (Université de Kinshasa).

Figure 1: *Pentaclethra macrophylla* Benth.

Extraction and chemical screening

The dried and powdered plant material (stem bark, 10 g) was repeatedly extracted by cold percolation with 95% ethanol (EtOH) and water (100 mL x 1) for 48 hours. Chemical screening was done in aqueous and organic extracts according to a well-known protocol as previously reported [15]. Fractions were filtered and concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. Extraction of anthocyanins was then done using 100 g of dried powdered plant material with acidified methanol (1% HCl) following an established protocol as previously reported [9-16]. Anthocyanins extracts were then defatted by n-hexane. Organic acids were extracted as previously reported [18].

Preparation of methanol extract and increasing polarity extracts

Plant powder (100 g) was macerated in methanol 80% (1L x 2) for 48 hours. After filtering the mixture, the hydro-alcoholic filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. The alcoholic extract was suspended in distilled water and sequentially partitioned with n-hexane, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate and methanol (1:1, v/v) three times at room temperature. The resulting fractions were evaporated to dryness on an evaporator apparatus. All extracts were stored at ± 4 °C.

Biological material

Blood samples used for the bioassays in this study were taken from known drepanocitary adolescent patients attending the “Centre de Médecine Mixte et d’Anémie SS” and “Centre Hospitalier Monkole”, both located in Kinshasa area, D. R. Congo. None of the patients had been transfused recently with Hb AA blood. All antisickling experiments were carried out with freshly collected blood. In order to confirm their SS nature, the above-mentioned blood samples were first characterized by hemoglobin electrophoresis on cellulose acetate gel at pH 8.5, as previously reported [5]. They were found to be SS blood and were then stored at ± 4 °C in a refrigerator. An informed consent was obtained from each patient participating in the experiment. All the research procedures have received the approval of Department of Biology Ethics Committee.

Antisickling assay

In order to evaluate the antisickling activity of our plant extracts, an *in vitro* antisickling assay was performed in which sickle cell blood was put in contact with plant extracts at different concentrations, according to the Emmel’s test procedure as previously reported [9-16]. Duplicate analyses were run for each extract.

Free radical scavenging assay

The DPPH free radical (1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) scavenging assay was performed as previously reported [19]. The radical scavenging activity of extracts for DPPH free radical was measured based on the principle of the reduction of the DPPH radical to a yellow-colored compound (diphenyl picrylhydrazin) in the presence of an antioxidant; the extent of the reaction depending on the hydrogen donating ability of the antioxidant. Briefly, a 100 μ M solution of DPPH radical in methanol was prepared. 3,5 mL of this solution was added to 0,5 mL solution of each extract in methanol at concentrations ranging from 0,1 to 1 mg/mL, thus obtaining the desired final concentrations in the reaction mixture. The mixture was shaken vigorously and incubated in the dark at room temperature for 30 min. The absorbance was measured at 515 nm using a spectrophotometer SP- 1105 Brand model. Methanol was used as a blank. The control solution consists of 0,5 mL of methanol and 3,5 mL of DPPH radical solution. The antiradical activity of a sample (calculated by the following formula) is given as percentage of reduced DPPH free radical: $\%I = [(OD\ control - OD\ sample)/OD\ control] \times 100$. The IC_{50} value (μ g/mL) is the effective concentration at which DPPH radicals were scavenged by 50%. L-ascorbic acid was used as positive control. Duplicate analyses were run for each extract.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical screening and Extraction yields

The phytochemical screening performed on the aqueous and organic extracts revealed the presence of polyphenols such as anthocyanins, leucoanthocyanins, quinones, tannins. Saponins, alkaloids, terpenes were also present while flavonoids, coumarines and sterols were not found in the plant. The presence of various secondary metabolites in the plant could justify its medical use. Indeed, *P. macrophylla* is reported to treat some gastrointestinal diseases including chronic diarrhea, dysentery and intestinal parasitoids [20]. Moreover, polyphenols compounds, which are significantly present in the plant, are well known for their large spectrum of pharmacological properties, including antimicrobial, antifungal, antiprotozoal, antiviral and antioxidant activities [22]. Therefore, there is more evidence that these plant’s

extracts contain some metabolites which inhibit the sickling process of erythrocytes. The promising candidates responsible of this biological activity are anthocyanins and organic acids since besides their remarkable well-known antioxidant properties they have shown *in vitro* antisickling activity [9-17, 19, 21]. Extraction yields of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* Benth. stem barks are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Extraction yields of *P. macrophylla* stem barks.

According to the results presented in figure 2, it is clearly shown that the unpolar solvents have fewer yields than polar ones. This reveals that the abundant metabolites in the stem barks of *P. macrophylla* are those which pass easily through the polar solvents.

The extraction yields of the anthocyanins and organic acids extracted from the stem barks powders of the plant are respectively 7.8% (3.99 g) and 1.32% (0.4 g). In comparison with some other results, e.g. *Dicliptera colorata* (7.04%), *Euphorbia hirta* (2.54%), and *Alchornea cordifolia* (1.28%), we found that, *P. macrophylla* exhibited a high content of anthocyanins.

Antisickling activity of different fractions from *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stems bark

Figures 3, 4 a, 4b, 4c and 4d illustrate respectively the morphology of SS blood erythrocytes alone in a NaCl 0.9% solution (control, fig. 3) and that of SS blood erythrocytes in the presence of n-hexane (fig. 4a), dichloromethane (fig. 4b), ethyl acetate (fig. 4c) and methanolic (Fig. 4d) soluble fractions of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem barks.

Figure 3: Morphology of drepanocytes of untreated SS blood (control) (x500) [NaCl 0,9% ; Na₂S₂O₅ 2%,].

Figure 4a: Morphology of drepanocytes treated with 50 µg/ml of n-hexane soluble fraction of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem barks (X500) [NaCl 0,9% ; Na₂S₂O₅ 2%,].

Figure 4b: Morphology of drepanocytes treated with 50 µg/ml of dichloromethane soluble fraction of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem bark (X500) [NaCl 0,9% ; Na₂S₂O₅ 2%,].

Figure 4c: Morphology of drepanocytes treated with 50 µg/ml of ethyl acetate soluble fraction of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem barks (X500) [NaCl 0,9% ; Na₂S₂O₅ 2%,].

Figure 4d: Morphology of drepanocytes treated with 50 µg/ml of methanolic soluble fraction of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem barks (X500) [NaCl 0,9% ; Na₂S₂O₅ 2%,].

Figure 3 shows that all the red blood cells (RBCs) adopt a sickle-shape in hypoxic conditions which, confirms the SS nature of the used blood samples (control). Mixed together with n-hexane, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate and methanol soluble fractions (Fig. 4, a-d) in the same experimental conditions, the majority of sickle erythrocytes present a different morphology: they recover the biconcave normal form. Normalization of sickle red cells is much better with n-hexane, dichloromethane, and methanol fractions than with ethyl acetate soluble fraction. This indicates that *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem barks have antisickling effects, thus justifying the use of this plant in Congolese traditional medicine. It was recently reported that the antisickling activity of some medicinal plant species used for the management of SCD by Congolese traditional healers is due to anthocyanins and phenolic/ triterpenic acids [9-16, 17]. The treated SS RBCs demonstrated a remarkable similarity to normal blood values.

Figure 5 shows the evolution of normalization rate of n-hexane, dichloromethane and methanol soluble fractions of *P. macrophylla* on drepanocytes.

Figure 5: Evolution of normalization rate of drepanocytes with *P. macrophylla* concentration extracts

As it can be seen on figure 5, the curves show that the normalization of drepanocytes increases with the extract concentration, reaching a maximum and constant value at 25 µg/mL. This minimal concentration corresponding to the maximal normalization rate is called minimal concentration of normalization (MCN). This corresponds to a normalization rate of 75.49% for n-hexane fraction, 78.37 % for dichloromethane fraction, and 84.36 % for the methanolic extract. The antisickling activity is dose dependent. These results show that the methanolic extract and dichloromethane fraction are more active than the n-hexane fraction.

Antisickling activity of anthocyanins and organic acids extracts from *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem bark

Figures 6a and 6b give theoptical micrograph phenotypes of SS blood treated with anthocyanins and organic acid crude extracts from *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem barks.

Figure 6a: Morphology of SS erythrocytes treated with anthocyanins extracts 10 µg/mL (X500) [NaCl 0,9% ; Na₂S₂O₅ 2%,].

Figure 6b: Morphology of SS erythrocytes treated with organic acids extracts 10 µg/mL (X500) [NaCl 0,9% ; Na₂S₂O₅ 2%,].

Figures 6a and 6b clearly indicate that in the presence of both anthocyanins and organic acids extracts, the majority of drepanocytes in SS blood reversed their sickle shapes to the normal biconcave form as compared to the negative control (Fig. 3). This indicates that anthocyanins and organic acids are the major antisickling agents of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* stem barks.

similar results confirming the antisickling activity of anthocyanins and organic acids (betulinic acid, maslinic acid and lunilaric acid) from some plants used in traditional medicine against SCD have been already reported [9-15, 17]. In fact, the properties of anthocyanins to bind to proteins such as Hb S could compete with the polymerization of this abnormal hemoglobin in tactoids and prevent the sickling of sickle cells [15]. In addition, anthocyanins (for which intestinal catabolism gives phenolic acids), well known for their antioxidant properties, could affect the Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ higher ratio in sickle cells and the stability of erythrocytes membranes by preventing the oxidation of membranes phospholipids [14]. As SCD is a chronic disease, using anthocyanins as medicinal foods or nutraceuticals would be a good approach instead of giving pharmaceutical products to sicklers during all their life.

Figure 7 shows the evolution of normalization rate of the anthocyanins and organic acids extracts on drepanocytes.

Figure 7: Evolution of normalization rate of drepanocytes with anthocyanins and organic acids extracts concentration of *P. macrophylla*.

The normalization of sickled cells with the anthocyanins and organic acids extracts increased with the extract concentration and reached a maximum and constant value at 25 µg/mL (MCN). This corresponds to a normalization rate of 78.96% for anthocyanins extracts and for organic acids extracts. Therefore, the antisickling activity of these active principles is dose dependent.

Free radical scavenging activity

The radical scavenging activity of different fractions is given in Table 1.

Fraction	IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)	Free radical Scavenging Activity
L-Ascorbic Acid (Positive control)	0.562 ± 0.212	1.776
Methanol extract	1.517 ± 0.053	0.659
Ethyl acetate fraction	14.35 ± 0.32	0.069
Dichloromethane fraction	No active	-
n-hexane fraction	No active	-
Anthocyanins extract	5.653 ± 0.212	0.177
Organic acids extract	5.064 ± 0.159	0.197

As it can be noticed from Table 1, methanol extract presents the lowest IC₅₀ value, compared to the positive control (high antioxidant activity), and followed by the organic acids extracts, the anthocyanins extracts and the ethyl acetate fraction respectively. There is more evidence that the antisickling activity of extracts from *Pentaclethra macrophylla* could be due not only to the presence of polyphenols known for their antioxidant properties but also to other metabolites such as triterpenoids that can easily pass through the dichloromethane fraction [17]. It has recently been reported over the last decades that reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a key role in the pathophysiology of various ischemic diseases including SCD. Indeed, it is postulated that in SCD, the sickling leads to the modification of the membrane flexibility, which makes it more sensitive and fragile towards free radicals or oxidants. The oxidative stress is likely due to intravascular sickling and transient vaso-occlusive event that lead to the decrease of nitric oxide (NO), as result of hemolysis [16]. Results presented in this paper evidenced the antisickling and scavenging effects of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* as attractive potential candidate for SCD therapy for improving the quality life of sicklers. As an antioxidant plant, *P. macrophylla* could prevent hemoglobin from oxidizing into methemoglobin, and therefore could inhibit the oxidative reactions by scavenging ROS before they can damage cells.

CONCLUSION

The present study evaluated the phytochemical screening and the *in vitro* antioxidant and antisickling activities of *P. macrophylla* stem barks. This plant species displayed promising antisickling and radical scavenging effects *in vitro*. The ability of anthocyanins and organic acids extracts to display such pharmacological properties may represent a rational explanation for the use of the plant by the traditional healers to treat SCD. Further studies involving the metabolomic profiling of the active fractions are in progress.

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